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Title: Can permeable pavements effectively retain microplastics from urban stormwater?

Abstract:

Stormwater runoff washes off urban surfaces and drives microplastics to receiving water bodies. The negative impact caused by this emergent pollutant in both the environment and human health, raises the need to control it. The potential use of Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems, and permeable pavements in particular, manage to significantly reduce suspended particles carried by runoff. The study aims to investigate how effective are permeable pavements at microplastic retention. The response of a permeable pavement was tested under the average rainfall regime of Valencia (Spain). The results showed a significant reduction in the number of microplastics in the effluent of a permeable pavement (94%). Polypropylene fragments were the most retained particles. Although the implementation of permeable pavements in the urban environment may help to reduce the content of microplastics in stormwater runoff discharges, more research is still needed.

Communication: Preferably paper/oral presentation